

ID	Day	BMS	Twitching	Grooming	Digging	Ear	Temp30
		Score	n°event/10 min	n°event/10 min	n°event/10 min	Score	
25	Baseline	NA	0	9	8	0	34,94
26	Baseline	NA	0	5	5	0	34,28
27	Baseline	NA	0	6	15	0	34,5
28	Baseline	NA	0	6	9	0	34,67
29	Baseline	NA	0	3	15	0	34,5
30	Baseline	NA	0	6	12	0	33,62
37	Baseline	NA	0	5	13	0	33,28
38	Baseline	NA	0	2	8	0	32,68
39	Baseline	NA	0	2	9	0	33,42
42	Baseline	NA	0	2	5	0	29,88
47	Baseline	NA	0	3	6	0	34,38
48	Baseline	NA	0	10	8	0	34,7
31	Baseline	NA	0	6	13	0	35,38
32	Baseline	NA	0	14	10	0	34,37
33	Baseline	NA	0	4	18	0	34,12
34	Baseline	NA	0	6	6	0	34,07
35	Baseline	NA	0	5	5	0	35,29
36	Baseline	NA	0	6	5	0	33,83
40	Baseline	NA	0	4	6	0	32,06
41	Baseline	NA	0	6	9	0	31,84
43	Baseline	NA	0	6	7	0	35,1
44	Baseline	NA	0	6	4	0	32,84
45	Baseline	NA	0	10	13	0	32,78
46	Baseline	NA	0	6	6	0	32,6
25	Day 0	0	9	0	0	2	35,82
26	Day 0	0	4	0	0	2	36,32
27	Day 0	0	9	3	0	2	36,98
28	Day 0	0	6	0	0	2	34,5
29	Day 0	0	3	11	0	2	37,08
30	Day 0	0	18	0	0	1	33,96
37	Day 0	0	22	8	0	2	32,63
38	Day 0	0	23	0	0	2	30,93
39	Day 0	0	5	0	0	2	33,08
42	Day 0	0	3	1	1	1.5	33,8
47	Day 0	0	0	4	0	1	35,66
48	Day 0	0	19	0	0	1.5	32,9
31	Day 0	0	2	1	0	1.5	35,47
32	Day 0	0	0	1	0	1.5	36,07
33	Day 0	0	1	0	0	2	34,27
34	Day 0	0	1	1	0	1.5	35,9
35	Day 0	0	0	4	0	1.5	36,1
36	Day 0	0	5	2	0	1.5	35,2
40	Day 0	0	4	0	0	1	33,47
41	Day 0	0	1	1	0	0.5	33,74
43	Day 0	0	5	9	0	0.5	33,86
44	Day 0	0	2	1	0	1.5	31,76
45	Day 0	0	1	12	0	1	32,72
46	Day 0	0	0	0	0	1.5	32,46

25	Day 1	0	1	4	0	2	
26	Day 1	0	1	12	2	1	37,86
27	Day 1	0	0	3	0	2	36,62
28	Day 1	0	1	8	0	1.5	37,76
29	Day 1	0	0	1	5	2	37,78
30	Day 1	0	1	0	0	2	36,77
37	Day 1						
38	Day 1	0	4	2	0	2	35,52
39	Day 1	0	1	0	0	2	35,32
42	Day 1	0	3	3	0	1	36,08
47	Day 1	0	4	8	5	0.5	37,84
48	Day 1	0	18	0	0	1.5	29,43
31	Day 1	0	0	2	3	0	36,02
32	Day 1	0	0	1	4	0.5	37,32
33	Day 1	0	0	6	3	0	35,79
34	Day 1	0	1	6	3	0.5	36,46
35	Day 1	0	0	4	4	0.5	37,18
36	Day 1	0	0	5	2	1	36,96
40	Day 1	0	3	7	3	0.5	36,14
41	Day 1	0	3	8	1	0	36,36
43	Day 1	0	2	1	0	0.5	36,1
44	Day 1	0	1	5	0	1	36,24
45	Day 1	0	0	5	4	1	35,96
46	Day 1	0	2	9	0	1	35,78
25	Day 7	1	0	19	6	0.5	39,58
26	Day 7	0	0	10	8	0.5	39,28
27	Day 7	0	0	7	4	0.5	39,3
28	Day 7	1	0	11	3	0.5	39,72
29	Day 7	1	0	4	4	0	40,52
30	Day 7	0	0	1	12	0.5	39,77
37	Day 7						
38	Day 7	0	0	5	7	0	36,2
39	Day 7	1	0	9	8	0	36,86
42	Day 7	1	0	2	12	0	36,1
47	Day 7	0	0	3	12	0.5	36,56
48	Day 7						
31	Day 7	1	0	2	11	0.5	39,24
32	Day 7	0	0	5	9	0	39,26
33	Day 7	0	0	4	9	0.5	38,52
34	Day 7	1	0	0	9	0.5	37,98
35	Day 7	1	0	4	2	0.5	38,95
36	Day 7	1	0	1	8	1	38,05
40	Day 7	0	0	12	11	0	36,52
41	Day 7	1	0	8	12	0	37,3
43	Day 7	0	0	5	11	0	36,98
44	Day 7	1	0	14	11	0	36,9
45	Day 7	0	0	13	11	0	37,14
46	Day 7	0	0	6	7	0.5	36,62
25	Day 14	2	0	19	1	0.5	40,37
26	Day 14	1	0	10	5	0.5	39,77

27	Day 14	1	0	9	2	0	40,13
28	Day 14	1	0	8	3	0.5	40,1
29	Day 14	1	0	1	15	0	39,97
30	Day 14	0	0	11	5	1	39,98
37	Day 14						
38	Day 14	1	0	9	7	0	33,48
39	Day 14	1	0	14	4	0.5	33,68
42	Day 14	1	0	5	14	0.5	33,12
47	Day 14	0	0	4	5	0	34,73
48	Day 14						
31	Day 14	1	0	6	1	0.5	39,02
32	Day 14	1	0	0	7	0.5	39,48
33	Day 14	1	0	9	4	1	39,45
34	Day 14	1	0	0	4	0	40,3
35	Day 14	1	0	3	3	0	38,43
36	Day 14	1	0	10	2	0.5	39,94
40	Day 14	0	0	7	1	0	34,4
41	Day 14	1	0	7	8	0	34,32
43	Day 14	1	0	9	5	0	33,44
44	Day 14	0	0	4	2	0	33,9
45	Day 14	1	0	6	6	0	33,18
46	Day 14	1	0	4	1	0	33,88
25	Day 21	2	0	12	4	0.5	34,27
26	Day 21	1	0	18	5	0	33,75
27	Day 21	2	0	10	8	0.5	33,16
28	Day 21	2	0	12	6	0.5	32,99
29	Day 21	2	0	4	7	0.5	32,09
30	Day 21	1	0	9	2	0.5	32,85
37	Day 21						
38	Day 21	2	0	6	5	0	31,62
39	Day 21	2	0	9	3	0.5	30,86
42	Day 21						
47	Day 21	1	0	2	10	0	32,26
48	Day 21						
31	Day 21	2	0	2	4	0	32,5
32	Day 21	1	0	5	2	0.5	30,39
33	Day 21	2	0	6	4	0	30,03
34	Day 21	2	0	10	1	0	31,89
35	Day 21	1	0	10	2	0.5	31,06
36	Day 21	1	0	9	1	0	32,3
40	Day 21	1	0	4	6	0	30,5
41	Day 21	2	0	4	9	0	31,7
43	Day 21	2	0	3	3	0	31,26
44	Day 21	1	0	10	7	0	31,78
45	Day 21	2	0	4	10	0	30,82
46	Day 21	2	0	9	5	0	29,46
25	Day 28	3					
26	Day 28	2					
27	Day 28	2					
28	Day 28	2					

29	Day 28	2
30	Day 28	2
37	Day 28	
38	Day 28	2
39	Day 28	2
42	Day 28	
47	Day 28	2
48	Day 28	
31	Day 28	3
32	Day 28	2
33	Day 28	3
34	Day 28	3
35	Day 28	2
36	Day 28	1
40	Day 28	2
41	Day 28	
43	Day 28	2
44	Day 28	2
45	Day 28	3
46	Day 28	2